

FOOD SAFETY MANAGEMENT

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Annotation: *The lack of single international requirements for the system of Product Safety and Quality Management in food enterprises ISO 22000 series "Food Safety Management System. The need to develop"requirements for all of the supply chain" came out, and it was introduced from September 2005.*

Key words: *HACCP , market relations, ISO 9001:2000, GMP, ISO 22000, "DSt ISO 22000:2010",*

Explaining the food safety management system that combines the ISO 22000 HACCP and ISO 9001:2000 standard, at the same time GMP (Good Manufacturing experience) combines the dastlabi requirements program and interprets its concepts. The main emphasis in this standard is on ensuring customer satisfaction through the effective management of food hazards, risk management and modernization of system processes. At the moment, the structure of the documentation makes it possible to conveniently integrate this system into quality management and environmental protection systems. Their latest research shows that the ISO 22000 series standard has become very popular, and in the last 2 years, enterprises that have been certified by this standard have increased by 3 times [1-2-4].

Currently, the system of Food Safety Management "DSt ISO 22000:2010" establishes requirements for quality management system in Uzbekistan. Adopted and implemented the standard" requirements for organizations participating in the chain of creation of food products" [5].

Thus, at present, the HACCP system is a universally developed system on the scale of the khalaro, which ensures the best quality and safety of food products at all stages of its life cycle. It was developed in the US and expressed in itself a model of risk management in food enterprises, currently distributed in many countries around the world and Europe.

The adoption of the law "on technical regulation" in the Republic of Uzbekistan was another impetus for the development of national legislation in the field of ensuring the safety of food products. The development and adoption of acts in the food sector has made an important contribution to the status of the existing technical regulations and participation in the process of universal European integration of Uzbekistan, harmonization and convergence of legislative norms.

In many European countries, the HACCP system is regarded as a component of the overall system of food hygiene measures. In the UK, the Food Safety Act 1990 and the Food Safety Regulation No. 1763 were adopted in 1995. These documents manifest themselves in the legislation, which indicates the requirements for all stages of the production chain [5-6].

In Germany, the decision of the Federal Government on hygiene of food products on the basis of the law on food products from 1997 Year 5 August 1974 year 15 August was adopted and is valid. In this decision *V etom postanovlenii ukazivaetsya, chto tot, kto proizvodit produkti pitaniya, podvergaet IX pererabotke II transportiruet, installation of Om xavfli dangerous by conducting the inspection, it is necessary to identify and guarantee the critical points for each of the processes that are taken safety measures davriy verification. For their identification, the principles of HACCP serve.*

On May 26, 1997, the legal decree №155 was adopted, which included the principles of the HACCP and ten applications of general and special measures in Article 3 of the decree. The enactment of the decree laid the groundwork for The Binding of the principles of HACCP for Food Network institutions [4].

Article 3 of the Legislative Decree No. 67/98 of 18 March 1998 on self-control of Portugal consists of the contents of the principles of the HACCP. In France, acts of a number of ministries implementing the HACCP system were issued in the mid-90s with the aim of implementing the norms of Chapter I of the law of the Consumer Code Book II. All these acts demonstrate vertical legislation, in which hygienic requirements are specified for individual categories of food products.

World experience shows that the legal management of the HACCP system is carried out not only by introducing the principles of the HACCP into the Acts governing the general hygiene of food products, but also by introducing separate special acts dedicated to the use of the principles of the HACCP. In Europe, for example, in the Netherlands, in 1998, the second

edition of the national document with the name "critical evaluation of the current HACCP system" was adopted. In Russia since July 1, 2001 the system "GOST R 51705.1-2001" kachestva. Upravlenie kachestvom pitshevix produktov na osnove printsipov HACCP. Obtshie trebovaniya " standard is adhered to. Initially, the system was developed in the 70-ies of the XX century and was used in the aerospace industry (with its help, quality and safety of food products for astronauts were controlled). In the mid-80s, the American Academy of Sciences offered it to serve all consumers. Mandatory compliance of food industry enterprises with HACCP requirements Europe [5].

HACCP-concept refers to the systematic identification, management and evaluation of hazardous omillarni, which seriously affects the safety of products. He first appeared in the US at the beginning of 1990 year. Work on the introduction of Nasr began in the countries of the European Union (EU) in 1993 year after the adoption of directives on hygiene of food products (93/43). In order to ensure the safety of products produced by enterprises of the Bunda food industry and to conduct monitoring of technological processes at the identified points, it was required to conduct a critical, risk-based analysis, which was determined by the parameters of technological processes.

The system of risk analysis and critical control points is a science-based system that allows to guarantee the safe production of the product through the control and identification of risk factors. The HACCP system is considered to be the only system that ensures the safety of food products, adopted by international organizations, which have proved its effectiveness. The use of the HACCP system allows the transition from testing of the final product to the development of prevention methods in ensuring the safety of food products.

The HACCP system should be based on a solid foundation.

This is the same in accordance with the production of the foundation:

- * Conscience production methods (GMP).
- Sanitary control methods (SNU).

GMP and SNU affect production conditions and therefore should be in accordance with the initial programs before the introduction of the HACCP system.

For the development and implementation of the HACCP system, it is necessary to apply seven principles that determine the procedure for the application, creation and implementation of the HACCP plan in the working state, for the production of this or that production.

1- Principle conduct an analysis of risks (risk factors).
2-principle. Determination of critical control points (CCP)
3-principle. Setting critical boundaries
4-principle. Development of monitoring system for CCP inspection
5- Principle Control standing CCP identify corrective actions applied in cases where he or she testifies to the monitoring results on these performances.

6- principle. Development of verification (verification) procedure confirming the factual operation of the HACCP system.

7-principle. Confirm all procedures and records related to these principles and apply them.

The principles of HACCP can be applied at all stages of food production, as well as in agricultural production, in the initial processing and processing of food products, in the stages of transportation and delivery to the customer, as well as in the systems of consumer consumption and sales [4-5].

LITERATURE:

1. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the quality and safety of food products" dated 30.08.1997 N 482-II (amended on 25.04.2003).

2. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Technical Regulation" of 2009.

3. SanPiN N. 0283-10 "Hygienic requirements for food safety" of the Republic of Uzbekistan

4. Global Food Safety Initiative Guidance Document, 4th edition, July 2004 (Руководящий документ Глобальной инициативы по пищевой безопасности, 4-е издание, июль 2004).

5. HACCP Standards Guide for Suppliers and External Manufacturers // Karft foods 2010, 107 с.

6. Davlyatova M.B., Sagdullayev Sh.Sh., Majidov K.X., Amonova Z.M, / THE USE OF VEGETABLE EXTRACTS IN THE PRODUCTION OF FLOUR SAND CONFECTIONERY// Scientific and technical journal "development of Science and technology" №5/2020 Pages 144-149.